

**YILDIZ TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY
DEPARTMENT OF MECHANICAL ENGINEERING**

CARGO DELIVERY DRONE DESIGN

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GRADUATE THESIS

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ISTANBUL, 2022

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LIST OF SYMBOLS

F	Force [N]
ρ	Density [g/cm^3]
σ	Stress [MPa]

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
FAA	Federal Aviation Administration
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
ICAO	International Civil Aviation Organization
FC	Flight Controller
VTX	Video Transmitter
Rx	Radio Receiver
Tx	Radio Transmitter
ESC	Electronic Motor Controller
FEM	Finite Element Method

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ABSTRACT

Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAV) or a drone, which were first used and developed in the military, have undergone significant modifications in recent years and are increasingly being used in civilian applications. Drones are currently utilized in both civil and military applications. They're used in firefighting, rescue, and specialized applications including surveillance and assault. Other than these, civil usage of drones as a hobby has increased after the cost of access to the drones started decreasing in recent years. Although, commercial use of the drones is not common. On this thesis, a cargo delivery drone with the cargo carrying capacity of 1 kg and the flight time of 22.8 minutes has been designed. For carrying a cargo, gripper system is used for the drone to be able to drop and pick up the cargo without any human interference. All the bolts used on the system are polyamide 66 material. Plastic bolts have lower weight and the stresses occurring on the bolts are appropriate for using plastic bolts. Both the gripper and drone parts will all be manufactured with polyamide 66 material. Polyamide 66 is most common used material along with carbon fiber on the drone bodies. Polyamide 66 can be injection molded to manufacture complex shaped parts. Material of the gripper system and the drone body is also polyamide 66 material. The drone is designed fail safe for a motor failure. The drone will keep hovering in case of a motor failure situation during flight (page 17). The bodies are designed with the cavity necessary for 3 batteries and other electronic components. A static gimbal is designed for holding the camera.

Keywords: Cargo delivery, drone, gripper

1. INTRODUCTION

An unmanned aerial vehicle (UAV), sometimes known as a drone, is an aircraft that does not have a human pilot, crew, or passengers on board and is either self-piloted or controlled by a ground-based controller and a communications system with the UAV. Drone technology has been used in a variety of applications due to advances in communication, processing, and sensing techniques during the last two decades. In recent years, UAVs are started to be used for journalism, search and rescue, disaster response, asset protection, wildlife monitoring, firefighting, communications relay, healthcare and agriculture. Apart from these, military purpose drones are also started playing a big strategic role in modern combat. Although, cargo delivery by drone is not as common as you think. The reason behind this is that strong winds preventing drones from flying, aviation administration regulations, and reaching customers in densely populated metropolitan areas are all problems that must be overcome. When deploying drones for cargo delivery, safety is just as important as delivery characteristics. This paper aims to design a cargo delivery drone and overcome some of the problems described above.

2. LITERATURE RESEARCH

Drones are categorized into five categories based on their weight: nano (under 250 g), micro air vehicles (250 g - 2 kg), miniature UAV (2–25 kg), medium (25–150 kg), and large (above 150 kg).^[1] Physical components of crewed and uncrewed aircraft of the same kind are often comparable. The cockpit and environmental control system, as well as life support systems, are the key exceptions. Some UAVs carry payloads (such as cameras) that are much lighter than an adult human, allowing them to be much smaller. Weaponized military UAVs are lighter than crewed counterparts with comparable weaponry, but carrying heavier payloads. Because small civilian UAVs lack life-critical equipment, they can be made of lighter but less durable materials and designs, and their electronic control systems can be less thoroughly tested. The quadcopter design has grown common for small UAVs, while it is rarely utilized for crewed aircraft. Miniaturization means that less-powerful propulsion technologies can be used that are not feasible for crewed aircraft, such as small electric motors and batteries. UAV control systems are frequently different from crewed craft. A camera and video link nearly usually replace the cockpit windows for remote human control, and radio-transmitted digital commands replace physical cockpit controls. Both crewed and uncrewed aircraft usually employ autopilot software, which has different feature sets. For long-range drones,

traditional internal combustion and jet engines are still used. However, for shorter-range missions, electric power has almost fully taken over. Lithium-polymer batteries (Li-Po) are used in most small drones, whereas hydrogen fuel cells are used in some bigger vehicles. Modern Li-Po batteries have a lower energy density than gasoline or hydrogen but electric motors, on the other hand, are less expensive, lighter, and quieter. Drone technology is still being developed every day. The purpose of developing complex multi-engine, multi-propeller installations is to improve aerodynamic and propulsive efficiency. Battery elimination circuitry, controlled by a microcontroller unit, can be utilized to centralize power distribution and reduce heating in such complicated power installations.

Another important subject about drones is that many governments have regulations about flying civil drones. Individual countries' civil aviation authorities are progressively regulating the use of drones. Regulatory regimes can vary greatly depending on the size and use of drones. The International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) began investigating the usage of drone technology in 2005 and published a study in 2011.^[2] France was one of the first countries to establish a national framework based on the report, and major aviation organizations like the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA) and the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) swiftly followed suit.^[3] The FAA released a rule in 2021 requiring all commercially used UAVs and all UAVs weighing 250g or greater, regardless of intent, to participate in Remote ID.

The typical electric motored drone's main parts are:

1. Drone body-A housing for all the electronic and mechanical parts.
2. Flight Controller (FC)-The main electronic board where ESC, Rx and VTX connected.
3. Electronic Speed Controller (ESC)-Electronic component which controls and regulates the speed of electric motors according to the commands taken from the FC.
4. Motors-Electrical machines that convert electrical energy into mechanical energy.
5. Propellers-Used to generate thrust by rotating at high speeds.
6. Radio Receiver and Transmitter (Rx-Tx)-Receives and sends information about flight between controller and the drone.
7. Global Positioning System (GPS)-Electronic component used to get the location of the drone on earth.
8. Camera-Used for either giving the controller a view of the drone or for recording.

9. Video Transmitter (VTX)-Transmits camera record to the controller live.
10. Battery-Generally Li-Po battery used for storing electrical energy.
11. Connection Cables-All the electrical components on drone are connected by electric cables.

There are a lot of different number of motors and configurations are used on drones currently. Figure 1 shows the most common motor configurations.

Figure 1. Common motor configurations of drones.

As shown on the figure 1, drones can have 4 to 8 motors. The most common used configuration is quad-rotor X. On all of the configurations above, half of the rotors are rotating clockwise and the other half are rotating counter clockwise direction. The reason for such configuration is to be able to rotate the drone along its central axis by keeping the stability which is called yawing. Yawing is achieved by slowing 2 (or 3 on Hexa-rotor and 4 on Octa-rotor) of the same direction rotating rotors for quad configuration. As the angular momentum in one direction increase, the drone starts yawing. All configurations' hovers or adjusts drone's altitude by applying equal thrust to all of the rotors. Forward and backward movements are achieved by increasing rotation speed of both of the front or the back side rotors.

Drone body material is commonly carbon fiber as it has good mechanical properties like high tensile strength with low density allowing the drone to be lighter. Although, carbon fiber material is a composite material and hard to manufacture complex drone bodies. Along with that, carbon fiber prices are expensive. Carbon fiber material is almost impossible to recycle and not so environmentally friendly material. Owing to these disadvantages, many companies manufacture their drone bodies with different types of plastic materials. Plastic bodies are easier to manufacture and cheaper but they don't have

a high tensile strengths advantage. It is essential to analyze the stresses on the body when manufacturing plastic body.

Designing a cargo delivery drone will have various advantages like sending a medicine to hard-to-reach areas etc.

3. DESIGN SPECIFICATION

There are not much of a cargo delivery drones available on the market but available non cargo carrying drones have an average flight time of 20 minutes. However, flight time depends on the price and type of drone. The average drone flight time is about 5-10 minutes for a beginner drone, 15-20 minutes for a mid-range drone, and 20-30 minutes for a prosumer vehicle. For example, DJI Phantom 4 Pro has a maximum flight time of 30 minutes even without carrying any cargo. DJI Phantom 4 Pro is considered one of the best drones on the market with a price of \$1,180.^[4] According to the market, the designed drone's flight time should not be less than 20 minutes.

DESIGN SPECIFICATION		
GROUP	SPECIFICATION	IMPORTANCE (1:not important, 10:must be)
Aesthetics	Drone color should be black or dark grey	5
Function	Should be able to carry 1 kg of cargo	9
	Flight time should be minimum of 20 minutes	10
	Should be able to pick the cargo up and drop it remotely	9
Design	Drone landing gear is required	8

4. DESIGN

4.1. Choosing Cargo Delivery System Type

The drone has to carry a cargo, for that, cargo carrier system can be designed 2 ways. First one is to design a box system under the drone to keep the cargo inside. The second one is to design a robotic arm, a gripper system under the drone. Designing a box like system will limit the cargo volume and won't fit the design specification. Box system can't pick the cargo up. On the other hand, drawback of the gripper system is it will cause bigger air resistance to the drone as it will have a higher overall volume with a cargo but a gripper system will be able to pick the cargo and drop it in the destination fully automatically with the help of a connected motor to the gripper. To fit to the design requirements, gripper system will be designed and connected under the drone. Technical drawings of the gripper can be found on appendix.

Figure 2. Gripper 3D model – closed.

Figure 3. Gripper 3D model – open.

Figure 4. Gripper carrying a cargo.

Figure 5. Gripper carrying a cargo – section view.

Figure 5 shows the section view of a package carrier part and end of the gripper. Gripper end is designed using a self-help principle. When the cargo is being lifted, the weight of the cargo will prevent the gripper from opening. With this design, there will not be any torque going to the pinion and the motor connected to the gripper. If there were a torque needed to hold the cargo, it would be necessary to use a stepper motor on the gripper but this design allows using a servo motor on the gripper as there is no need of a holding torque.

As for the motor SPT5435LV servo motor is chosen and shown on the figure 6. Servo motor can be precision controlled. Opening and closing of the gripper will be controlled precisely. Figure 7 shows the dimensions of the servo motor. Motor weight is 60 g.

Figure 6. Servo motor.

Figure 7. Servo motor dimensions.

Figure 8. Servo motor and gripper connection.

For non military drones' material, thermoplastics such as variants of polyamide, polyester, and polystyrene, are popular choices because they are inexpensive to make into complex parts using injection molding processes. Both drone body and the gripper parts will be manufactured using polyamide 66 material. If the an equivalent stress exceeds the yield stress of the polyamide 66 material, the material can be changed or the design can be altered. Assuming the gripper material is nylon 66, the total mass of the gripper system can be calculated. The SolidWorks program gives the total volume of the design which is equal to 32042.27 mm^3 and the density of the polyamide 66 material is 1.14 g/cm^3 .

$$m_{gripper, total} = 32042.27 \text{ mm}^3 * 0.00114 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mm}^3} + 60 \text{ g} = 96.5 \text{ g}$$

4.2. General Calculations and Selection of Drone Parts

When designing a drone, the first component should be chosen is which type of the motor to be used and the number of the rotors. Other components are depending on the number of motors and the motor voltage. For example, some flight controller boards have 4 Electric Speed Controller (ESC) outputs and some has 8 ESC output. Also, working voltages of the motors differ, the battery should be chosen accordingly. The motor model for the drone is chose as 'T-MOTOR U3 KV700 4S Waterproof Power Type Dustproof Brushless Motor' and shown on the figure 10. Motor test data and the motor dimensions are available on the manufacturer website and these data given on figures 9 and 10.

Figure 9. T-MOTOR U3 KV700 DC motor.

Figure 10. Motor dimensions.

Item No.	Voltage (V)	Prop	Throttle	Current (A)	Power (W)	Thrust (G)	RPM	Efficiency (G/W)	Operating Temperature (°C)
U3 KV700	11.1	T-MOTOR 12*4CF	50%	2.5	27.75	350	4000	12.61	40
			65%	4.8	53.28	550	4900	10.32	
			75%	6.6	73.26	700	5500	9.56	
			85%	9.1	101.01	870	6300	8.61	
			100%	11.1	123.21	1000	6600	8.12	
		T-MOTOR 13*4.4CF	50%	2.9	32.19	400	3800	12.43	42
			65%	5.6	62.16	650	4900	10.46	
			75%	7.9	87.69	830	5300	9.47	
			85%	10.5	116.55	1000	6000	8.58	
			100%	12.6	139.86	1100	6400	7.87	
	T-MOTOR 14*4.8CF	50%	4.1	45.51	550	3500	12.09	43	
		65%	7.7	85.47	890	4500	10.41		
		75%	10.7	118.77	1060	4900	8.92		
		85%	14.5	160.95	1300	5500	8.08		
		100%	17.3	192.03	1460	5800	7.60		
	14.8	T-MOTOR 11*3.7CF	50%	3.2	47.36	460	5300	9.71	43
			65%	6	88.80	710	6500	8.00	
			75%	8.2	121.36	870	7500	7.17	
			85%	11	162.80	1080	8200	6.63	
			100%	13	192.40	1230	8700	6.39	
T-MOTOR 12*4CF		50%	3.8	56.24	580	5000	10.31	43	
		65%	7.4	109.52	880	6300	8.04		
		75%	10.3	152.44	1100	7300	7.22		
		85%	14	207.20	1360	7700	6.56		
		100%	16.8	248.64	1600	8300	6.44		
T-MOTOR 13*4.4CF	50%	4.7	69.56	730	4900	10.49	47		
	65%	9	133.20	1120	6100	8.41			
	75%	12.3	182.04	1400	6800	7.69			
	85%	16	236.80	1600	7400	6.76			
	100%	19.4	287.12	1800	7850	6.27			

Figure 11. Motor test data.

Test Report			
Test Item	U3 KV700	Report NO.	U.00001
Specifications			
Internal Resistance	50mΩ	Configuration	12N14P
Shaft Diameter	4mm	Motor Dimensions	Φ41.8×30.75mm
AWG	18#	Cable Length	600mm
Weight Including Cables	128g	Weight Excluding Cables	97g
No. of Cells (Lipo)	3-4S	Idle Current@10v	0.5A
Max Continuous Power 180S	500W	Max Continuous Current 180S	25A

Figure 12. Motor general information.

On the figure 11, it can be seen that motor performs best on 13*4.4 propeller working on 14.8 V. Best performing propeller will be used on the drone. 13*4.4 propeller means that the propeller diameter is 13 inches and has the pitch of 4.4 inches. 14.8 V corresponds to 4 S battery. When designing a drone, the total thrust that the motors generate should be at least 1.5 times higher than the total weight of the drone for proper acceleration. Drone can't accelerate if the motors can only generate maximum thrust equal to the drone 's total weight. Another important information about the motor is that highest throttle has the

lowest efficiency as can be seen on the figure 11.

As for the camera, 'Caddx Nebula Pro' model camera chosen. The camera can record with 720p quality on 120 fps. The camera is shown on the figure 14 and the camera dimensions are shown on the figure 14. Total weight of the camera is 6 g.

Figure 13. Caddx Nebula Pro camera.

Figure 14. Camera dimensions.

As for the battery, 'HRB 4S 14.8v 5000mAh 50C Li-Po Battery' model battery is chosen and shown on the figure 16. Its dimensions are: 155x48x32mm and has the weight of 492 g. The battery has 5000mAh capacity.

Figure 15. HRB model 5000mAh 14.8 V battery.

4.3. Determining the Motor Configuration

The battery is chosen but the capacity of this battery might not fit to the design requirements (20 mins of flight time with a cargo). More than 1 battery can be used connecting them in parallel on the drone. Connecting 2 batteries in parallel doubles the capacity and keeps the voltage of the battery same. The main drone components are chosen except the flight controller board and some of its components like VTX, GPS etc. The flight controller weight is much smaller than other components. Average weight of a controller board is around 10-20 g. The weight of the flight controller is ignorable for a general calculation of the flight time. The amount of battery and rotor to be used is not clear yet. All the possibilities will be calculated and the optimal design will be picked. Estimated drone body weight is considered to be 100 g for 4 rotor, 130 g for 6 rotor and 160 g for 8 rotor body. These values are only estimated values and the calculations will be rechecked with more precise values after the design completed. So far for any rotor and battery combination, the gripper with the weight of 96.5 g and the camera with the weight of 6 g will be used. Additional average 160 g of weight for the electronic components, bolts, nuts and connection cables will be added for estimation of the flight time. Power usage of the flight controller board, other electronic components and the camera is estimated to be 15 W all together. Figure 11 shows how much power each motor will use on each throttle. With the data gathered, we can estimate the flight time for

various number of batteries and different motor numbers when used. Figure 16 shows all the possible designs with corresponding flight time. For fitting to the design requirements, minimum of 3 batteries

NUMBER OF MOTORS	DRONE BODY WEIGHT	WEIGHT OF GRIPPER AND ELECTRONIC COMPONENTS	NUMBER OF BATTERIES	TOTAL WEIGHT OF BATTERIES	TOTAL WEIGHT OF MOTORS	TOTAL DRONE WIEGHT WITH CARGO (grams)	MINIMUM TOTAL THRUST RQUIRED (grams)	THRUST PER MOTOR (grams)	POWER USAGE FOR EACH MOTOR (Watts)	CAMERA+BOARD POWER USAGE (Watts)	TOTAL POWER CONSUMPTION OF THE DRONE (Watts)	Flight Time (Hours)	Flight Time (Mins)	
4 MOTOR	100 g	262.5 g	1 (5,000 mAh=74 Wh)	492 g	512 g	2366.5	3549.75	887.4375	95	15	395	0.18	10.8	
			2 (10,000 mAh=148 Wh)	984 g		2858.5	4287.75	1071.9375	125		500	0.296	17.76	
			3 (15,000 mAh=222 Wh)	1476 g		3350.5	5025.75	1256.4375	157		628	0.35	21	
			4 (20,000 mAh=296 Wh)	1968 g		3842.5	5763.75	1440.9375	190		760	0.39	23.4	
6 MOTOR	130 g		1 (5,000 mAh=74 Wh)	492 g	768 g	2652.5	3978.75	663.125	53		333	0.22	13.2	19.2
			2 (10,000 mAh=148 Wh)	984 g		3144.5	4716.75	786.125	75		450	0.32	19.2	
			3 (15,000 mAh=222 Wh)	1476 g		3636.5	5454.75	909.125	96		576	0.38	22.8	
			4 (20,000 mAh=296 Wh)	1968 g		4128.5	6192.75	1032.125	118		708	0.41	24.6	
8 MOTOR	160 g		1 (5,000 mAh=74 Wh)	492 g	1024 g	2938.5	4407.75	550.96875	40		335	0.22	13.2	19.8
			2 (10,000 mAh=148 Wh)	984 g		3430.5	5145.75	643.21875	55		440	0.33	19.8	
			3 (15,000 mAh=222 Wh)	1476 g		3922.5	5883.75	735.46875	70		560	0.39	23.4	
			4 (20,000 mAh=296 Wh)	1968 g		4414.5	6621.75	827.71875	85		680	0.43	25.8	

Figure 16. Estimated flight time of various designs.

Need to be used for the flight time to be higher than 20 mins in any motor configuration. It is clear that increasing the number of motors on the drone also increases the flight time with the same amount of battery. The reason for that is motors' efficiency increases when the motor throttle decrease. Using more motors means that the same thrust can be achieved with lower throttle. Another point to be noted is that increasing the battery and motor number also increases the cost of manufacturing. Figure 16 shows that there will not be much of a flight time gains in increasing motor number. In case of a motor failure, the design should be able to land the drone safely. With the help of a gyroscope, the drone software can perceive a motor failure. To prevent the falling off the drone and to keep the stability, the drone software can turn off the motor in the opposite direction of the failed motor. This will only work if the remaining motors' total thrust is higher than the total weight of the drone. On the 4 motored design, the total weight of the drone with 3 batteries is 3350.5 g and the maximum thrust each motor can achieve is 1800 g. The remaining 2 motors will not be able to stabilize the drone in case of a motor failure situation. 3600 g of thrust is not enough to stabilize 3350.5 g of drone drone because of the center of mass might not be same as the central axis. On the 6 motored design, in case of a motor failure, when the controller turns off the motor on the opposite of the failed motor, remaining 4 motors can achieve 7200 g of thrust which is higher than the weight of the 6 motored drone. This will prevent the falling of the drone in case of a motor failure situation. Because of the reasons above, 6 motor will be used on the design. There is only around 2 minutes of flight time difference between using 3 or 4 batteries. For only 2 minutes of extra flight time, using 4 batteries instead of 3 is not reasonable. 3 batteries will be used on the design.

Another important drone component is the flight controller board. There are various

flight controllers available for FPV drones. There is also All in One (AIO) flight controller type which ESC's and VTX, Rx, Tx are all integrated to one board. For example, 'Fly woo' GOKU GN745 AIO 40A BL32 Stack + HM600 VTX is popular controller board. It has built in 4in1 ESC and VTX, also can be added GPS and Rx, Tx. 4in1 ESC means it has a 4 electric speed controller outputs (figure 17). Dimensions of this board is 33.5x33.5x6.5 mm and the total weight is 11.5 g.^[5]

Figure 17. 'Fly woo' GOKU GN745 AIO 40A BL32 Stack + HM600 VTX board.

The total number of motors that were used in the design was 7. 1 servo motor on gripper and 6 on the propellers. This board is not suitable for our design. For the design, a custom flight controller board will be used. The flight controller to be used should have 7 ESC outputs and should also connect to the internet via inserted SIM card. GPS and gyroscope components should also be added to the controller. By using an internet connection, range limit for controlling the drone is removed. For the custom board, a space for a 35x35mm bolt connection and a 10 mm thickness will be created inside the drone body.

4.4. Calculating General Dimensions and Preparation of a Design Draft

Dimensions for all the selected components are known and now a body for these components can be designed. The propeller diameter was 13 inches which is equal to 330.2 mm. The propeller diameter defines the distance between the propeller's central axis and the drone's center. With all the known dimensions, a 2D draft for the drone is drawn on the next page. When placing the components, keeping the center of mass of the components near to the drone body's central axis is essential but even if it is not designed like that, it wouldn't be a problem because the thrust of the motors can be calibrated to keep the drone in balance when programming the flight controller.

SCALE	DATE	DRAWN	STUDENT No	YILDIZ TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY	
1:5	2022/05/15	Muhammetnur A.	18065917	Mechanical Engineering Department	
	Drone Body Draft-Upper View			MATERIAL	GROUP/DRAWING No
			Draft-1		

SCALE	DATE	DRAWN	STUDENT No	YILDIZ TECHNICAL UNIVERSITY Mechanical Engineering Department	
1:5	2022/05/15	Muhammetnur A.	18065917	MATERIAL	GROUP/DRAWING No
	Drone Body Draft-Right View				Draft-2

4.5. Creating Solid Model from the Draft

Design is started with designing the main body. Body divided to 2 parts, upper and lower body. Bodies are designed with 1 mm thickness. For manufacturability, drone arms will be separate from the body and will be connected to the lower body by a bolted connection. Figures 18, 19, 20, 21, 22 and 23 gives brief information about the design and the technical drawings of all the parts are available on the appendix. Figure 24, 25 and 26 shows the rendered model of the drone.

Figure 18. Upper body part.

Figure 19. Lower body part.

Figure 20. Drone arm design.

Figure 21. Drone arm-top view.

Figure 22. Drone arm assembly.

Figure 23. General drone assembly.

Figure 24. Rendered image of the drone – corner view.

Figure 25. Rendered image of the drone – front view.

Figure 26. Rendered image of the drone equipment.

5. FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS OF THE BODY AND THE GRIPPER

All the parts of the drone and the gripper will be manufactured from polyamide 66 material which is the most common used material for the drone bodies. Polyamide 66 can be used for manufacturing complex parts using injection mold method and offers good physical and chemical properties. The material has the density of $\rho=1.14 \text{ g/cm}^3$, yield strength of $\sigma_{yield} = 80 \text{ Mpa}$.^[6] The maximum equivalent stress of the material parts be less than the yield strength of the material. The worst case scenario for the gripper is that it tries to lift a high weighted cargo. In that case, even if the 6 of the motors tries to pull the cargo, maximum thrust the motors can produce is $1.8 \text{ kg} \times 6 = 10.8 \text{ kg}$. In the worst case scenario, the maximum force the gripper system can face is 10.8 kg force. 10.8 kg force is equivalent to 106 N. The assembly is meshed, and the force is applied at the end of the gripper on ANSYS software. Figures 27, 28 and 29 shows the FEM analysis of the gripper system. Figure 29 shows that the maximum stress the gripper can face is 13.23 Mpa which is way lower than the yield strength of the material. $80 \text{ MPa} / 13.23 \text{ Mpa}$ gives the safety factor of around 6. In general engineering applications, this safety factor is unacceptable. High safety factors means that the part is being manufactured with unnecessary high

amount of the material and occupies bigger space, increasing the manufacturing costs. In the drone case, safety factor of 6 means that the part might have been lighter and could save some energy but the gripper dimensions are standard dimensions. Total weight of the gripper system without motor was 36.5 g (page 12) which is so little weight proportion of the whole drone system. Going out of the standards and aesthetics is not convenient just for decreasing the weight and the manufacturing costs a bit.

Figure 27. Applied force to the gripper system.

Figure 28. Maximum strain of the gripper system.

Figure 29. Maximum stress formed on the gripper system.

Drone body material is also polyamide 66. The body has the same yield strength. As there is bolted connection between drone arm and the lower body part, they will be analyzed together. Maximum thrust one motor can create is 1,8 kg which is equivalent to 17.6 N. 17.6 N of force is applied to each motor on the assembly. Figures 30 and 31 shows the maximum strain and stress that occurs on the lower body as the result of the motor's maximum thrust.

Figure 30. Maximum strain of the lower drone body part.

Figure 31. Drone arm and lower body contact type-section view.

Figure 32. Maximum von-mises stress-section view.

Figure 31 shows the contact type of the arm and lower body part which is a frictionless contact. The bolts are bonded contact to the lower body and the arm part. The maximum stress occurs on the right bolt. The bolt materials is also polyamide 66 with the yield strength of 80 Mpa. Maximum von-mises stress on the assembly is equal to 31 Mpa as seen on the figure 32. $80 \text{ Mpa} / 31 \text{ Mpa}$ gives the safety factor of 2.58 which is around acceptable. The drone body thickness was 1 mm which is a standard thickness for a body.

Thicknesses lower than 1 might also be convenient by means of the stresses as it can be seen on the analysis result but because of the reasons noted on the gripper system, the body thickness will remain as 1 mm. Full design is mechanically durable.

CONCLUSION

As a result, drone body is designed with 1 mm thickness. The connection bolts and the body materials are both polyamide 66 with the density of $\rho=1.14 \text{ g/cm}^3$. Figure 33 shows the total volume of the drone assembly without motors, camera, propellers, gripper system and electronic components. The weight of the gripper system, motors, camera is already known or calculated above precisely.

Figure 33. Total volume of the assembly.

All the parts shown on the figure 33 will be manufactured with polyamide 66 material. The total weight of the drone parts, camera gimbal, bolts and landing gear is calculated as:

$$m_{assembly, total} = 823,666 \text{ mm}^3 * 0.00114 \frac{\text{g}}{\text{mm}^3} = 939 \text{ g}$$

The assumed weight for the body for 6 propeller design was 130 g (page 19). There is a major difference between the actual body weight and the assumed weight. Total drone weight can be calculated again with the precise data and the motor thrust capacity can be rechecked.

PART	WEIGHT
Drone body and landing gear	939 g
3 batteries	1476 g
Gripper and servo motor	96.5 g
6 motors	768 g
Camera	6 g
Estimated electronic components and propellers	~160 g
Cargo	1000 g
Total	4445 g

Total weight of the designed drone is 4445 g. Maximum thrust that the motors can generate is $6 \times 1,800 \text{ g} = 10,800 \text{ g}$. Maximum thrust the motors can generate is still above 2 times the total weight with cargo. This shows that the drone can accelerate easily even without 100% throttle of the motors. As noted on the page 19, even on the motor failure situation, 4 motors can generate 7,200 g of thrust which is enough to hover the drone with even 4 motors. All the parts are manufacturable and the system is mechanically durable.

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APPENDIX

Pages:33-42-Gripper parts and assembly

Pages:43-46-Drone parts and assembly (Custom landing gear)

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

NAME

SIGNATURE

DATE

TITLE:

DRAWN

Muhammetnur A.

2022.05.14

CHK'D

APPV'D

MFG

Q.A

MATERIAL:

DWG NO.

Gripper_Part 1

A4

SCALE:1:1

SHEET 1 OF 1

FINISH:		DEBURR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES		DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		REVISION	
NAME		SIGNATURE		DATE		TITLE:	
DRAWN	Muhammetnur A.			2022.05.14			
CHK'D							
APPV'D							
MFG							
Q.A				MATERIAL:		DWG NO.	
						Gripper Part 2	
						A4	
				SCALE:2:1		SHEET 1 OF 1	

FINISH:		DEBURR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES		DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		REVISION	
NAME		SIGNATURE		DATE		TITLE:	
DRAWN	Muhammetnur A.			2022.05.14			
CHK'D							
APPV'D							
MFG							
Q.A							
MATERIAL:				DWG NO.		A4	
				Gripper Part 3			
				SCALE:2:1		SHEET 1 OF 1	

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE
DRAWN	Muhammetnur A.		2022.05.14
CHK'D			
APPV'D			
MFG			

TITLE:

GEAR INFORMATION		MATERIAL:
MODULE	1.125	
NUMBER OF TEETH	24	
PITCH DIAMETER	27	

DWG NO. **Gripper Part 4** A4

SCALE:2:1 SHEET 1 OF 1

4

3

2

1

F

F

E

E

D

D

C

C

B

B

A

A

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

TITLE:

	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE		
DRAWN	Muhammetnur A.		2022.05.14		
CHK'D					
APPV'D					
MFG					
Q.A					

MATERIAL:

DWG NO.

Gripper Part 6

A4

SCALE:2:1

SHEET 1 OF 1

4

3

2

1

4

3

2

1

F

F

E

E

D

D

C

C

B

B

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

NAME

SIGNATURE

DATE

TITLE:

DRAWN Muhammetnur A. 2022.05.14

CHK'D

APPV'D

MFG

Q.A

MATERIAL:

DWG NO.

Gripper Rivet

A4

SCALE:2:1

SHEET 1 OF 1

4

3

2

1

A

A

4

3

2

1

F

F

E

E

D

D

C

C

B

B

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

NAME

SIGNATURE

DATE

TITLE:

DRAWN

Muhammetnur A.

2022.05.14

CHK'D

APPV'D

MFG

GEAR INFORMATION

MATERIAL:

DWG NO.

MODULE

1.125

NUMBER OF TEETH

13

PITCH DIAMETER

14.625

Motor Pinion

A4

SCALE:2:1

SHEET 1 OF 1

4

3

2

1

A

A

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

NAME

SIGNATURE

DATE

TITLE:

DRAWN Muhammetnur A.

2022.05.14

CHK'D

APPV'D

MFG

Q.A

MATERIAL:

DWG NO.

Motor Connector

A4

SCALE:1:1

SHEET 1 OF 1

ITEM NO.	DWG NO:	DESCRIPTION	QTY.
1	Gripper_Part 1	CUSTOM PART	4
2	Gripper Part 2	CUSTOM PART	4
3	Gripper Part 3	CUSTOM PART	2
4	Gripper Part 4	CUSTOM PART	1
5	Gripper Part 5	CUSTOM PART	1
6	Gripper Part 6	CUSTOM PART	2
7	Gripper Rivet	PA 66 RIVET	8
8	Motor Pinion	CUSTOM PART	1
9	ISO 7380 - M3 x 12 - 12S		3
10	ISO - 4035 - M3 - N		2

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

NAME

SIGNATURE

DATE

TITLE:

DRAWN

Muhammetnur A.

2022.05.14

CHK'D

APPV'D

MFG

Q.A

MATERIAL:

DWG NO.

Gripper Assembly

A4

SCALE:1:1

SHEET 1 OF 1

4

3

2

1

4

3

2

1

F

F

E

E

D

D

C

C

B

B

A

A

SHELL THICKNESS:	1 mm
------------------	------

FINISH:	DEBURR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES
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DO NOT SCALE DRAWING	REVISION
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	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE		
DRAWN	Muhammetnur A.		2022.05.14		
CHK'D					
APPV'D					
MFG					
Q.A					

TITLE:	Upper body	A4
DWG NO.		
SCALE:1:10	SHEET 1 OF 1	

4

3

2

1

SHELL THICKNESS: 1 mm

FINISH:

DEBURR AND
BREAK SHARP
EDGES

DO NOT SCALE DRAWING

REVISION

	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE
DRAWN	Muhammetnur A.		2022.05.14
CHK'D			
APPV'D			
MFG			
Q.A			

TITLE:

MATERIAL:

DWG NO.

Lower body

A4

SCALE:1:10

SHEET 1 OF 1

FINISH:		DEBURR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES		DO NOT SCALE DRAWING		REVISION	
NAME		SIGNATURE		DATE		TITLE:	
DRAWN	Muhammetnur A.			2022.05.14			
CHK'D							
APPV'D							
MFG							
Q.A				MATERIAL:		DWG NO.	
						Arm	
						A4	
SCALE:1:5						SHEET 1 OF 1	

ITEM NO:	DWG NO:	DESCRIPTION
1	Uppder body	Custom part
2	Propeller	T-MOTOR 13*4 4CF
3	Arm	CUSTOM PART
4	Lower body	CUSTOM PART
5	Camera	CADDX NEBULA PRO
6	-	CUSTOM LANDING GEAR
7	Gripper assm.	GRIPPER SYSTEM

FINISH:	DEBURR AND BREAK SHARP EDGES	DO NOT SCALE DRAWING	REVISION
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	NAME	SIGNATURE	DATE
DRAWN	Muhammetnur A.		2022.05.14
CHK'D			
APPV'D			
MFG			
Q.A			

TITLE:	Drone assembly	A4
DWG NO.		
SCALE:1:20	SHEET 1 OF 1	

MATERIAL: